

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Paper

Heal Like A Pro: The Homoeopathic Sports Injury Toolkit

Shaikh Mohammed Hamza Jamaluddin¹, Dr. Hasina Mushtaq Mhaishale^{*2}

¹Student, Parul Institute of Homoeopathy and Research, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat

²Principal, Omar Homoeopathic Medical College and Research Centre, Ranjani Jalna, Maharashtra

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 16 Apr. 2025

Keywords:

Sports Injury,
Homoeopathy, Constitution,
Susceptibility, Holistic
Approach, Individualization,
Healing, Complications,
Auxiliary Measures,
Physical Therapy,
Prevention, Physiotherapy

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15230391

ABSTRACT

Sports injuries are a common occurrence among childhood and young age of those who are active in physical activities and sports. Sports injury often leads to pain, inflammation, and impaired performance. Homoeopathy, a system of medicine based on the principle of “like cures like”, offers a potential therapeutic approach for these injuries. Homoeopathy presents promising prospects for managing sports injuries due to its holistic approach catering to an individual constitution and susceptibility. There are a number of homoeopathic medicines which act in sports injury. Out of which 12 most commonly used medicines are discussed with their therapeutic indications. Along with the medicines auxiliary measures should be taken for quick results.

INTRODUCTION

A sports injury is any kind of damage that happens in our body during physical activity, exercise, or sports. It can affect the bones, muscles, tendons, ligaments, and other tissues. Sports injuries can range from minor bumps and bruises to serious tears and breaks. Homoeopathy has gained considerable attention over the years for its holistic approach to healing and managing various health conditions, including sports injuries. The key factor for this is the way homoeopathy works by

matching the symptom picture of injury, including constitutional factors where relevant, such as susceptibility to injury, or long-term weakness or tendency to slow healing. The right remedy acts powerfully and stimulates the healing process and as a result stiffness, pain and inflammation in an acute injury will typically reduce more quickly, returning you to full strength promptly and without any complications. Homoeopathy is also worth the long-term effects of sports injury too. It resolves

***Corresponding Author:** Dr. Hasina Mushtaq Mhaishale

Address: Principal, Omar Homoeopathic Medical College and Research Centre, Ranjani Jalna, Maharashtra

Email ✉: hasina.mhaishale@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

old injuries and underlying weaknesses, freeing you up to get back.

Types – Broadly sports injuries are divided into two types:

- Acute Sports Injury - An injury that occurs suddenly during physical activity, exercise, or sports is known as Acute Sports Injury
- Chronic Sports Injury - An injury which is caused by repeated overuse of muscle groups or joints. Chronic sports injury also occurs due to poor technique and structural abnormalities.

Apart from the broad classification there are many types of sports injuries. Some of the most commonly seen sports injury are:

- Abrasion
- Bruise

- Concussion
- Laceration
- Sprain
- Strain
- Tendinitis
- Cartilage Tear
- Dislocation
- Fracture

Homeopathic Sports Injury Toolkit –

There are different types of sports injury for which a number of medicines are there in homoeopathy which act on sports injury. Out of all those medicines 12 most commonly used medicines are discussed with their therapeutic indications as a homoeopathic sports injury kit.

Homoeopathic Sports Injury Tool Kit	
● Arnica Montana	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is used in first line treatment for physical trauma. ● It also act on the psychological effects of recent injuries ● It is used in treatment of bruising, swelling and pain associated with most traumatic injuries.
● Bryonia Alba	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is used in treatment of stress fractures, shoulder injuries, knee injuries or after knee surgery, as well as lower back pain. ● Pain gets worse on doing anything that causes motion, including deep breathing, coughing or turning over in bed. ● Pain gets better by firm, immobilizing pressure, bandaging, or lying on the painful part.
● Calcarea Fluorica	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is specifically used in injury caused due to muscle strain and overstretching of ligaments and tendons. ● Injuries result in pain and swelling, especially hard nodular swelling. ● It can be taken as a tonic to improve tone in muscles and ligaments.
● Calcarea Phosphorica	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is the first remedy to think about after a fracture, especially if you are prone to slow healing. ● It boosts natural healing ability and promotes the formation of callus in fractures. ● It can be taken for a period of time to rebuild strength in bones after a fracture.
● Ferrum Phosphoricum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is used in the treatment of injuries of the right shoulder, including rotator cuff injuries, and tendinitis affecting the shoulder. ● It is one of the best medicines for right sided frozen shoulders. ● There is pain when moving or lifting the arm, and the pain gets worse when lying in bed at night.
● Hecla Lava	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is used in the injuries of bones and connective tissues. ● It is specifically used in cases of bone spur cause due to injury.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hypericum Perforatum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is used in injuries of the parts which are rich in nerves. ● It is mostly used in spinal injuries and injuries to the coccyx, fingers, toes and head injuries. ● Injuries have a particular sharp, shooting and neuralgic character of pain.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rhododendron 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is one of the most useful remedies for groin injury. ● It is especially indicated in cases where the testes are swollen and painful, and the pain is tearing and paralyzing.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rhus Toxicodendron 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is used for injuries caused by repetitive strain and overexertion. ● It is helpful in all kinds of traumatic injuries, sprains and strains often accompanied by stiffness and burning. ● Its main indications are where the condition is worse for rest and on beginning movement, and better after continued movement. ● The complaint gets worse in cold and damp conditions, and better for warm bathing and warm applications.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ruta Graveolens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It has an affinity for tendons, ligaments and cartilage, and in injuries to these connective tissues. ● It is used in injuries caused by excessively strenuous activity. ● There may be lameness or weakness. ● It is also useful in injuries to the periosteum.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strontium Carbonicum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is used in treatment of ankle injuries. ● It is used especially where there is continued swelling and pain long after the original injury, with feelings of weakness in the affected ankle.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Symphytum Officinale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is used to promote healing of fractures ● It is used especially in cases where there is difficulty healing, or where there are torn muscles, tendons or ligaments. ● It is used in case a blow to the eye area causes pain in eyeball.

Note: In homoeopathy there are a number of remedies which are effective in treating sports injury. It is important to know when it is appropriate to use homoeopathy as a standalone therapy and when it is best to use side by side with conventional methods. No medication should be taken without proper consultation. Prescribing the right remedy takes practice and requires skill.

Auxiliary Measures –

Homeopathy should not only be the treatment considered following a sports injury. However, alongside physical therapy (physiotherapy) can improve outcomes significantly, and give better and faster results. Auxiliary measures include things like a diet plan, exercise, counseling, cleanliness, hygiene, and medical attention. Auxiliary measures are used to both prevent and advance health. Physiotherapy helps in rehabilitating the injured site and, depending on

the injury, may include exercises to promote strength and flexibility of injured bone and muscles. Homoeopathic medicine along with physical therapy helps to get back in the game – or on the running track or dance floor much more quickly.

CONCLUSION

Sports injury is a kind of damage that happens in the body during physical activity, exercise, or sports which affect the bones, muscles, tendons, ligaments, and other tissues. Sports injuries are commonly caused by overuse, direct impact, or the application of force that is greater than the body part can structurally withstand. Common injuries include bruises, sprains, strains, joint injuries. Homoeopathy can be a valuable approach in managing sports injuries either acute or chronic with careful consideration of constitution and susceptibility. Homeopathy, when combined with

physical therapy, can significantly improve sports injury outcomes. A homoeopathic sports injury kit discusses 12 commonly used homoeopathic medicines and their therapeutic indications for treating sports injuries. Auxiliary measures like diet, exercise, counseling, cleanliness, hygiene, and medical attention can also be used to prevent and advance health. This combination can help return to the game quickly.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.niams.nih.gov/health-topics/sports-injuries>
2. <https://www.betterhealth.vic.gov.au/health/healthy-living/sports-injuries#types-of-sports-injuries>
3. The Organon of Medicine by Samuel Hahnemann, 6th edition, translated by William Boericke
4. Boericke's New Manual of Homoeopathic Materia Medica with Repertory by William Boericke, reprint edition 2020, published by B. Jain Publisher
5. Allen's Key-notes Rearranged & Classified with Leading Remedies of the Materia Medica & Bowel Nosodes Including Repertorial Index by H. C. Allen, 10th Edition (2005), published by B. Jain Publisher.

HOW TO CITE: Shaikh Mohammed Hamza Jamaluddin¹, Dr. Hasina Mushtaq Mhaishale*, Heal Like A Pro: The Homoeopathic Sports Injury Toolkit, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2025, Vol 3, Issue 4, 1994-1997. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15230391>

